

D7.2

API Libraries for R and Python for the Programmable Corpora Prototype “DraCor”: “rdracor” and “pydracor”

Authors of the Report: Henny Sluyter-Gäthje, Peer Trilcke, Ingo Börner
Developers of the Software Libraries: Ivan Pozdniakov, Henny Sluyter-Gäthje,
Eduard Grigoriev, Frank Fischer

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D7.2 DraCor API Libraries for R and Python

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Authors: Henny Sluyter-Gäthje, Peer Trilcke, Ingo Börner

Concept and Research Software Engineering: Ivan Pozdniakov, Henny Sluyter-Gäthje, Eduard Grigoriev, Frank Fischer

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About this Deliverable

This Deliverable D7.2 was prepared as part of Work Package 7 in the CLS INFRA project. The deliverable consists of two programming libraries for the Python and R programming languages, each of which has been published on the relevant portals for the respective programming language (PyPi for Python and CRAN for R). The corresponding entries on the portals as well as the program code published under open source license can be accessed here.

R library “rdacor”

- <https://cran.r-project.org/package=rdacor>
- <https://github.com/dracor-org/rdacor>

Python library “pydracor”

- <https://pypi.org/project/pydracor>
- <https://github.com/dracor-org/pydracor>

1. Publishable Summary

Accessing literary corpora via application programming interfaces (APIs) proves to be a promising approach in the development of an infrastructural ecosystem for Computational Literary Studies (CLS). The use of APIs is further facilitated by so-called “API wrappers”, i.e. programming libraries that simplify working with the API directly from within a programming language. For the system DraCor (“Drama Corpora Platform”), which is being developed as a prototype for Programmable Corpora within the framework of CLS INRFA, and for its DraCor API, such libraries were developed in the two widely used programming languages R and Python and published on the corresponding platforms: “rdracor” was published on the platform CRAN, “pydracor” on the platform PyPi.

2. Details About the Publication of two API Libraries: “rdracor” and “pydracor”

As CLS INFRA Deliverable 7.1 “On Programmable Corpora” argues,¹ accessing literary corpora via application programming interfaces (APIs) proves to be a promising approach in the development of an infrastructural ecosystem for Computational Literary Studies (CLS). The use of APIs is further facilitated by so-called “API wrappers”, i.e. programming libraries that simplify working with the API by wrapping API functionalities directly into the development environments.

For the system DraCor (“Drama Corpora Platform”, <https://dracor.org/>), which is being developed as a prototype for Programmable Corpora within the framework of CLS INFRA, and for its DraCor API, such libraries were developed in the two widely used programming languages R and Python and published on the corresponding platforms: “rdracor” was published on the platform CRAN (Comprehensive R Archive Network), “pydracor” on the platform pypi (Python Package Index). “rdracor” can be installed with `install.packages("rdracor")` and can be included into R projects with `library(rdracor)`. “pydracor” can be installed with the command `pip3 install pydracor` on a machine with Python and pip available.

Both packages provide the same functionalities in that they make it easy to obtain metadata and data for corpora, individual texts and text segments or text elements (such as characters) via the DraCor API. In addition, “rdracor” provides functions that allow working with the data provided by DraCor for network analysis of plays and pydracor facilitates the creation of subcorpora through filtering. Finally, in some cases, functions have been developed that are specific to the requirements of the respective programming language, e.g., the “rdracor” function `tei_to_df` parses a text in the DraCor standard format TEI-XML into the tabular data format of a data frame (“df”), which is widely used in the programming language “R”.

¹ Cf. Börner, Trilcke (2023): CLS INFRA D7.1 On Programmable Corpora. Report and Prototype. [submitted to the European Commission February 28, 2023; after review by the European Commission, Deliverable D7.1 will be available online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7664964>].

2.1 “rdracor”

2.1.1 Publication Information on CRAN

Cf. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/rdracor/index.html>

rdracor: Access to the 'DraCor' API

Provide an interface for 'Drama Corpora Project' ('DraCor') API:

<<https://dracor.org/documentation/api>>.

Version: 0.7.2

Imports: jsonlite (≥ 1.6), utils, data.table (≥ 1.12.2), xml2 (≥ 1.2.2), igraph (≥ 1.2.4.1),

httr (≥ 1.4.1), tibble (≥ 3.1.8), purrr (≥ 0.3.5), stringr (≥ 1.4.1), tidyr (≥ 1.2.1), Rdpack

(≥ 2.4)

Suggests: testthat (≥ 2.1.0)

Published: 2023-01-23

Author: Ivan Pozdniakov [aut, cre]

Maintainer: Ivan Pozdniakov <bucherr at yandex.ru>

BugReports: <https://github.com/dracor-org/rdracor/issues>

License: GPL (≥ 3)

URL: <https://github.com/dracor-org/rdracor>

NeedsCompilation: no

Citation: [rdracor citation info](#)

Materials: [README NEWS](#)

CRAN checks: [rdracor results](#)

Documentation: Reference manual: [rdracor.pdf](#)

Downloads:

Package source: [rdracor_0.7.2.tar.gz](#)

Windows binaries: r-devel: [rdracor_0.7.2.zip](#), r-release: [rdracor_0.7.2.zip](#), r-oldrel:

[rdracor_0.7.2.zip](#)

macOS binaries: r-release (arm64): [rdracor_0.7.2.tgz](#), r-oldrel (arm64):

[rdracor_0.7.2.tgz](#), r-release (x86_64): [rdracor_0.7.2.tgz](#), r-oldrel (x86_64):

[rdracor_0.7.2.tgz](#)

Linking: Please use the canonical form <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rdracor> to link to this page.

2.1.2 Functions Provided

Tab. 01 lists the functions of the "rdracor" package and gives a brief description. For a detailed description and information about parameterization of the functions see the "rdracor" reference manual.²

function	short description
dracor_api	Send a GET request to DraCor API and parse the results
dracor_api_info	Retrieve 'DraCor' API info
dracor_sparql	Submit SPARQL queries to DraCor API
get_character_plays	Retrieve plays having a character identified by 'Wikidata ID'
get_dracor_meta	Retrieve information on available corpora
get_net_cooccur_edges	Retrieve co-occurrence edges list for a play as a data frame
get_net_cooccur_gexf	Retrieve co-occurrence network for a play in 'GEXF'
get_net_cooccur_graphml	Retrieve co-occurrence network for a play in 'GraphML'
get_net_cooccur_igraph	Retrieve an igraph co-occurrence network for a play
get_net_cooccur_metrics	Retrieve co-occurrence network metrics for a play
get_net_relations_igraph	Retrieve an igraph relations network for a play
get_play_cast	Retrieve data for characters in a play
get_play_metadata	Retrieve metadata for a play
get_play_rdf	Retrieve an RDF for a play
get_text_chr_spoken	Retrieve lines and stage directions for a play
get_text_tei	Retrieve a text for a play in 'TEI'
label_cooccur_igraph	Extract labels for plotting 'cooccur_igraph' object
summary.dracor	Retrieve metadata for all plays in selected corpora
tei_to_df	Retrieve a text for a play as a data frame

Tab. 01: Functions provided by "rdracor"

² Cf. [Appendix 2](https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/rdracor/rdracor.pdf) resp. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/rdracor/rdracor.pdf>

2.2 “pydracor”

2.2.1 Project Description on PyPi

Cf. <https://pypi.org/project/pydracor>

pydracor 1.0.0

Released: Feb 23, 2023

pip install pydracor

Project links: <https://github.com/dracor-org/pydracor>

License: MIT License (mit)

Author: Eduard Grigoriev, Henny Sluyter-Gäthje

Keywords: drama corpus, drama, corpus, pydracor, dracor, api, wrapper

Project description

pydracor is a Python package which provides access to the DraCor API.

2.2.2 Functions Provided

Tab. 02 lists the functions of the "pydracor" package and gives a brief description. For coding examples see the project description in PyPi.³

function	short description	on object
dracor_info	Get API info. Shows version numbers of the dracor-api app and the underlying eXist-db	DraCor
corpora	List available corpora. Get info about the corpora of the Drama Corpus	DraCor
corpora_names	Get all available corpora names	DraCor
corpora_titles	Get all available corpora titles	DraCor
corpus_name_to_field	Map corpus name to the field value	DraCor
corpus_name_to_repository	Map corpus name to the repository value	DraCor
corpus_name_to_title	Map corpus name to the title (full name)	DraCor
corpus_name_to_uri	Map corpus name to the api uri	DraCor
field_to_corpus_name	Map field value to the corpus name	DraCor
play_title_to_corpus_name	Map play title to the corpus name	DraCor
play_name_to_corpus_name	Map play name to the corpus name	DraCor

³ Cf. [Appendix 3](#) resp. <https://pypi.org/project/pydracor/>

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play_id_to_field	Map play id to the field value	DraCor
field_to_play_id	Map field value to the play id	DraCor
play_id_to_play_title	Map play id to the play title	DraCor
play_title_to_play_id	Map play title to the play id	DraCor
play_id_to_play_name	Map play id to the play name	DraCor
play_name_to_play_id	Map play name to the play id	DraCor
sparql	Submit SPARQL queries with query parameter	DraCor
plays_by_character_wikidata_id	List plays having a character identified by Wikidata ID	DraCor
summary	DraCor summary	DraCor
corpus_info	List corpus content. Lists all plays available in the corpus including the id, title, author(s) and other metadata	Corpus
play_ids	Get all corpus' play ids	Corpus
play_names	Get all corpus' play names	Corpus
play_titles	Get all corpus' play titles	Corpus
written_years	Map play id to the written year	Corpus
premiere_years	Map play id to the premiere year	Corpus
print_years	Map play id to the print year	Corpus
normalized_years	Map play id to the normalized year	Corpus
metadata	List of metadata for all plays in a corpus	Corpus
metadata_csv	Get metadata for all plays in corpus as CSV	Corpus
filter	Filter Plays of a Corpus	Corpus
authors_summary	Authors' summary for a corpus	Corpus
authors_summary_str	String representation of authors_summary method	Corpus
summary	Summary for a corpus	Corpus
play_info	Get metadata and network metrics for a single play	Play

metrics	Get network metrics for a single play	Play
get_cast	Get a list of characters of a play	Play
cast_csv	Get a list of characters of a play (CSV).	Play
num_of_male_characters	Get the number of male characters in a play	Play
num_of_female_characters	Get the number of female characters in a play	Play
num_of_unknown_characters	Get the number of characters of unknown gender in a play	Play
tei	Get TEI document of a single play	Play
rdf	Get RDF document of a single play	Play
csv	Get network data of a play as CSV	Play
gexf	Get network data of a play as GEXF	Play
relations_csv	Get relation data of a play as CSV	Play
relations_gexf	Get relation data of a play as GEXF	Play
relations_graphml	Get relation data of a play as GRAPHML	Play
spoken_text	Get spoken text of a play (excluding stage directions).	Play
spoken_text_by_character	Get spoken text for each character of a play	Play
stage_directions	Get all stage directions of a play	Play
stage_directions_with_speakers	Get all stage directions of a play including speakers	Play
summary	Play summary	Play
summary	Character summary	Character

Tab. 02: Functions provided by “pydracor”

D7.2 DraCor API Libraries for R and Python

Appendix

D7.2 DraCor API Libraries for R and Python

Appendix 1: “rdracor” Readme

rdracor

Authors: Ivan Pozdniakov, Frank Fischer

License: [GPL-3](#)

The goal of **rdracor** is to provide an R interface for the [DraCor API](#) (DraCor: Drama Corpora Project). Website of the project: dracor.org.

Installation

```
#install.packages("remotes") #if you don't have remotes installed
remotes::install_github("dracor-org/rdracor")
```

General info on corpora

Retrieving general information about available corpora:

```
library(rdracor)
```

```
corpora <- get_dracor_meta()
```

```
summary(corpora)
```

```
#> DraCor hosts 15 corpora comprising 3035 plays.
```

```
#>
```

```
#> The last updated corpus was German Drama Corpus (2023-01-02 18:15:22).
```

```
plot(corpora)
```

Number of plays for each corpus

Plays in the corpus

```

ger <- get_dracor(corpus = "ger")
summary(ger)
#> 598 plays in German Drama Corpus
#> Corpus id: ger, repository: https://github.com/dracor-org/gerdracor
#> Description: Edited by Frank Fischer and Peer Trilcke. Features more than 550 German-language
    plays from the 1650s to the 1940s. For a corpus description and full credits please see
    the [README on GitHub](https://github.com/dracor-org/gerdracor).
#> Written years (range): 1646–1947
#> Premiere years (range): 1650–1981
#> Years of the first printing (range): 1560–1962

```

You can get all corpora at once:

```

all <- get_dracor()
summary(all)
#> 3035 plays in 15 corpora:
#> Corpora id:
#> fre (1560 plays), ger (598 plays), rus (212 plays), cal (205 plays), ita (139 plays), swe (68
    plays), hun (41 plays), greek (40 plays), gersh (38 plays), shake (37 plays), rom (36
    plays), als (30 plays), span (25 plays), bash (3 plays), tat (3 plays)
#> Written years (range): 43–1970
#> Premiere years (range): –472–1992
#> Years of the first printing (range): 1170–2017

```

Play metadata

With `get_play_metadata()` you can get miscellaneous data for a play:

```

get_play_metadata(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
                  corpus = "ger",
                  full_metadata = FALSE) #use full_metadata = FALSE for faster download
#> $id
#> [1] "ger000088"
#>
#> $name
#> [1] "lessing-emilia-galotti"
#>
#> $corpus
#> [1] "ger"
#>
#> $title
#> [1] "Emilia Galotti"
#>
#> $author
#> $author$name
#> [1] "Lessing, Gotthold Ephraim"
#>
#> $author$warning
#> [1] "The single author property is deprecated. Use the array of 'authors' instead!"
#>
#>
#> $authors
#> # A tibble: 1 × 4
#>   name                fullname                shortname refs
#>   <chr>                <chr>                <chr>     <list>
#> 1 Lessing, Gotthold Ephraim Gotthold Ephraim Lessing Lessing <df [2 × 2]>
#>
#> $genre
#> [1] "Tragedy"
#>
#> $libretto
#> [1] FALSE
#>
#> $allInSegment
#> [1] 30
#>
#> $allInIndex
#> [1] 0.6976744

```

```

#>
#> $cast
#> # A tibble: 13 × 12
#>   id      name isGroup gender numOf...1 numOf...2 numOf...3 degree weigh...4 close...5
#>   <chr> <chr> <lgl> <chr> <int> <int> <int> <int> <int> <dbl>
#> 1 der_prinz Der ... FALSE MALE 17 157 4002 8 20 0.75
#> 2 der_kamm... Der ... FALSE MALE 2 6 33 1 2 0.444
#> 3 conti Conti FALSE MALE 2 24 604 1 2 0.444
#> 4 marinelli Mari... FALSE MALE 19 221 4343 9 30 0.8
#> 5 camillo_... Cami... FALSE MALE 1 6 78 1 1 0.444
#> 6 claudia Clau... FALSE FEMALE 13 73 1581 7 19 0.6
#> 7 pirro Pirro FALSE MALE 4 25 263 5 7 0.545
#> 8 odoardo Odoa... FALSE MALE 12 108 2441 6 15 0.667
#> 9 angelo Ange... FALSE MALE 2 28 487 2 2 0.48
#> 10 emilia Emil... FALSE FEMALE 7 64 1702 6 13 0.667
#> 11 appiani Appi... FALSE MALE 5 48 852 4 8 0.522
#> 12 battista Batt... FALSE MALE 4 11 152 4 7 0.6
#> 13 orsina Orsi... FALSE FEMALE 6 64 2111 4 8 0.6
#> # ... with 2 more variables: betweenness <dbl>, eigenvector <dbl>, and
#> # abbreviated variable names 1numOfScenes, 2numOfSpeechActs, 3numOfWords,
#> # 4weightedDegree, 5closeness
#>
#> $segments
#> # A tibble: 43 × 4
#>   type number title speakers
#>   <chr> <int> <chr> <list>
#> 1 scene 1 Erster Aufzug | Erster Auftritt <chr [2]>
#> 2 scene 2 Erster Aufzug | Zweiter Auftritt <chr [2]>
#> 3 scene 3 Erster Aufzug | Dritter Auftritt <chr [1]>
#> 4 scene 4 Erster Aufzug | Vierter Auftritt <chr [2]>
#> 5 scene 5 Erster Aufzug | Fünfter Auftritt <chr [1]>
#> 6 scene 6 Erster Aufzug | Sechster Auftritt <chr [2]>
#> 7 scene 7 Erster Aufzug | Siebenter Auftritt <chr [2]>
#> 8 scene 8 Erster Aufzug | Achter Auftritt <chr [2]>
#> 9 scene 9 Zweiter Aufzug | Erster Auftritt <chr [2]>
#> 10 scene 10 Zweiter Aufzug | Zweiter Auftritt <chr [2]>
#> # ... with 33 more rows
#>
#> $yearWritten
#> NULL
#>
#> $yearPremiered
#> [1] "1772-03-13"
#>
#> $yearPrinted
#> [1] "1772"
#>
#> $yearNormalized
#> [1] 1772
#>
#> $wikidataId
#> [1] "Q782653"
#>
#> $subtitle
#> [1] "Ein Trauerspiel in fünf Aufzügen"
#>
#> $relations
#> # A tibble: 4 × 4
#>   directed type source target
#>   <lgl> <chr> <chr> <chr>
#> 1 TRUE parent_of odoardo emilia
#> 2 TRUE parent_of claudia emilia
#> 3 TRUE associated_with marinelli der_prinz
#> 4 TRUE associated_with camillo_rota der_prinz
#>
#> $source
#> $source$name
#> [1] "TextGrid Repository"
#>
#> $source$url

```

```
#> [1] "http://www.textgridrep.org/textgrid:rksp.0"
#>
#>
#> $originalSource
#> [1] "Gotthold Ephraim Lessing: Werke. Herausgegeben von Herbert G. Göpfert in Zusammenarbeit
      mit Karl Eibl, Helmut Göbel, Karl S. Guthke, Gerd Hillen, Albert von Schirmding und Jörg
      Schönert, Band 1-8, München: Hanser, 1970 ff."
```

Play network

You can extract a co-occurrence network (undirected weighted graph) for a specific play:

```
emilia <- get_net_cooccur_igraph(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
plot(emilia)
```


You can use the package {igraph} to work with this object as a graph:

```
library(igraph)
edge_density(emilia)
#> [1] 0.3717949
graph_cohesion(emilia)
#> [1] 1
```

In addition, you can get a summary with network properties and gender distribution:

```
summary(emilia)
#> ger: lessing-emilia-galotti - co-ocurrence network summary
#> Lessing, Gotthold Ephraim: Emilia Galotti (1772)
#>
#>      Size: 13 (3 FEMALES, 10 MALES, 0 UNKNOWN)
#>      Density: 0.37
#>      Degree:
#>      - Maximum: 9 (Marinelli)
```

```

#> Distance:
#>   - Maximum (Diameter): 6
#>   - Average: 3.03
#> Clustering:
#>   - Global: 0.54
#>   - Average local: 0.67
#> Cohesion: 1
#> Assortativity: -0.45

```

Similarly, you can use function `get_net_relations_igraph()` to build a network based on relationships data:

```

nedorosl_relations <- get_net_relations_igraph(play = "fonvizin-nedorosl",
                                              corpus = "rus")
plot(nedorosl_relations)

```



```

summary(nedorosl_relations)
#> rus: fonvizin-nedorosl - relations network summary
#> Фонвизин, Денис Иванович: Недоросль (1782)
#>
#> Size: 15 (3 FEMALES, 12 MALES, 0 UNKNOWN)
#> Relations: 8
#> Простаков <--> Г-жа Простакова : spouses
#> Скотинин <--> Г-жа Простакова : siblings
#> Г-жа Простакова ---> Митрофан : parent_of
#> Простаков ---> Митрофан : parent_of
#> Еремеевна ---> Митрофан : associated_with
#> Софья ---> Стародум : related_with
#> ...and 2 more

```

Text of a play

You can get text of a play in different forms:

- as a raw TEI (optionally parsed with {xml2}):

```
get_text_tei(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
#> {xml_document}
#> <TEI id="ger000088" lang="ger" xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
#> [1] <teiHeader>\n <fileDesc>\n <titleStmt>\n <title type="main">Emil ...
#> [2] <standOff>\n <listEvent>\n <event type="print" when="1772">\n <d ...
#> [3] <text>\n <front>\n <titlePage>\n <docAuthor>Gotthold Ephraim Les ...
```

- as a character vector:

```
text_godunov <- get_text_chr_spoken(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
                                     corpus = "ger")
head(text_godunov)
#> [1] "Klagen, nichts als Klagen! Bittschriften, nichts als Bittschriften! – Die traurigen
Geschäfte; und man beneidet uns noch! – Das glaub' ich; wenn wir allen helfen könnten:
dann wären wir zu beneiden. – Emilia? Eine Emilia? – Aber eine Emilia Bruneschi – nicht
Galotti. Nicht Emilia Galotti! – Was will sie, diese Emilia Bruneschi? Viel gefodert;
sehr viel. – Doch sie heißt Emilia. Gewährt! Es ist wohl noch keiner von den Räten in
dem Vorzimmer?"
#> [2] "Nein."
#> [3] "Ich habe zu früh Tag gemacht. – Der Morgen ist so schön. Ich will ausfahren. Marchese
Marinelli soll mich begleiten. Laßt ihn rufen. – Ich kann doch nicht mehr arbeiten. –
Ich war so ruhig, bild' ich mir ein, so ruhig – Auf einmal muß eine arme Bruneschi,
Emilia heißen; – weg ist meine Ruhe, und alles! –"
#> [4] "Nach dem Marchese ist geschickt. Und hier, ein Brief von der Gräfin Orsina."
#> [5] "Der Orsina? Legt ihn hin."
#> [6] "Ihr Läufer wartet."
```

- as a data frame:

```
get_text_df(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
#> # A tibble: 1,174 × 10
#>   text          type type_...1 who   scene scene...2 subdiv...3 line_id subdiv...4 scene...5
#>   <chr>         <chr> <chr> <chr> <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int> <int>
#> 1 Die Szene,... stage "" <NA> Erst... act 1 stage 1 1 1 1
#> 2 an einem A... stage "" der_... Erst... act 1 ... sp 1 |... 2 2 2
#> 3 Klagen, ni... p "" der_... Erst... act 1 ... sp 1 |... 3 3 2
#> 4 Indem er n... stage "" der_... Erst... act 1 ... sp 1 |... 4 3 2
#> 5 Eine Emili... p "" der_... Erst... act 1 ... sp 1 |... 5 3 2
#> 6 Er lieset. stage "" der_... Erst... act 1 ... sp 1 |... 6 3 2
#> 7 Viel gefod... p "" der_... Erst... act 1 ... sp 1 |... 7 3 2
#> 8 Er untersch... stage "" der_... Erst... act 1 ... sp 1 |... 8 3 2
#> 9 Es ist woh... p "" der_... Erst... act 1 ... sp 1 |... 9 3 2
#> 10 Nein. p "" der_... Erst... act 1 ... sp 2 |... 10 4 2
#> # ... with 1,164 more rows, and abbreviated variable names 1type_attributes,
#> # 2scene_path, 3subdiv_path, 4subdiv_id, 5scene_id
```

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D7.2 DraCor API Libraries for R and Python

Appendix 2: “rdracor” Reference Manual

Package ‘rdracor’

January 23, 2023

Type Package

Title Access to the 'DraCor' API

Description Provide an interface for 'Drama Corpora Project' ('DraCor') API: <<https://dracor.org/documentation/api>>.

Version 0.7.2

License GPL (>= 3)

Encoding UTF-8

Imports jsonlite (>= 1.6), utils, data.table (>= 1.12.2), xml2 (>= 1.2.2), igraph (>= 1.2.4.1), httr (>= 1.4.1), tibble (>= 3.1.8), purrr (>= 0.3.5), stringr (>= 1.4.1), tidyr (>= 1.2.1), Rdpack (>= 2.4)

RoxygenNote 7.2.1

RdMacros Rdpack

Suggests testthat (>= 2.1.0)

URL <https://github.com/dracor-org/rdracor>

BugReports <https://github.com/dracor-org/rdracor/issues>

NeedsCompilation no

Author Ivan Pozdniakov [aut, cre] (<<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2450-7004>>)

Maintainer Ivan Pozdniakov <bucherr@yandex.ru>

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dracor_api	<i>Send a GET request to DraCor API and parse the results</i>
------------	---

Description

Function `dracor_api()` sends a GET request to DraCor API with a specified expected type and parses results depending on selected expected type.

Usage

```
dracor_api(
  request,
  expected_type = c("application/json", "application/xml", "text/csv", "text/plain"),
  parse = TRUE,
  default_type = FALSE,
  split_text = TRUE,
  as_tibble = TRUE,
  ...
)
```

Arguments

<code>request</code>	Character, valid GET request.
<code>expected_type</code>	Character, 'MIME' type: one of "application/json", "application/xml", "text/csv", "text/plain".
<code>parse</code>	Logical, if TRUE (default value), then a response is parsed depending on <code>expected_type</code> . See details below.
<code>default_type</code>	Logical, if TRUE, default response data type is returned. Therefore, a response is not parsed and <code>parse</code> is ignored. The default value is FALSE.
<code>split_text</code>	Logical, if TRUE, plain text lines are read as different values in a vector instead of returning one character value. Default value is TRUE.

<code>as_tibble</code>	Logical, if TRUE, data frame will be returned as a tidyverse tibble (<code>tbl_df</code>). The default value is TRUE.
<code>...</code>	Other arguments passed to a parser function.

Details

There are four different 'MIME' types (aka internet media type) that can be retrieved for DraCor API, the specific combination of possible 'MIME' types depends on API command. When `parse = TRUE` is used, the content is parsed depending on selected 'MIME' type in `expected_type`:

```
application/json  jsonlite::fromJSON()
application/xml   xml2::read_xml()
text/csv          data.table::fread()
text/plain        No need for additional preprocessing
```

Value

A content of a response to GET method to the 'DraCor' API. If `parse = FALSE` or `default_type = TRUE`, a single character value is returned. Otherwise, the resulting value is parsed according to a value of `default_type` parameter. The resulting structure of the output depends on the selected `default_type` value, the respective function for parsing (see `default_type`) and additional parameters that are passed to the function for parsing.

See Also

[dracor_sparql](#)

Examples

```
dracor_api("https://dracor.org/api/info", expected_type = "application/json")
```

<code>dracor_api_info</code>	<i>Retrieve 'DraCor' API info</i>
------------------------------	-----------------------------------

Description

`dracor_api_info()` returns information about 'DraCor' API: name of the API, status, existdb version, and API version.

Usage

```
dracor_api_info()
```

Details

No parameters are expected.

Value

A data frame with version of 'DraCor' API, 'existdb' and status.

See Also

[dracor_api](#)

Examples

```
dracor_api_info()
```

dracor_sparql	<i>Submit SPARQL queries to DraCor API</i>
---------------	--

Description

`dracor_sparql()` submits SPARQL queries and parses the result.

Usage

```
dracor_sparql(sparql_query = NULL, parse = TRUE, ...)
```

Arguments

<code>sparql_query</code>	Character, SPARQL query.
<code>parse</code>	Logical, if TRUE the result is parsed by <code>xml2::read_xml()</code> , otherwise character value is returned. Default value is TRUE.
<code>...</code>	Additional arguments passed to dracor_api .

Value

SPARQL xml parsed.

See Also

[get_dracor](#)

Examples

```
dracor_sparql("SELECT * WHERE {?s ?p ?o} LIMIT 10")
# If you want to avoid parsing by xml2::read_xml():
dracor_sparql("SELECT * WHERE {?s ?p ?o} LIMIT 10", parse = FALSE)
```

get_character_plays *Retrieve plays having a character identified by 'Wikidata ID'*

Description

get_character_plays() requests plays that include a character that can be found in 'Wikidata' by its id. get_character_plays() sends a request and parses the result to get those plays as a data frame.

Usage

```
get_character_plays(char_wiki_id)
```

Arguments

char_wiki_id Character value with 'Wikidata ID' for a character. 'Wikidata ID' can be found on https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page. Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.

Value

Data frame, in which one row represents one play. Information on author(s) name, character name, play name, URL and ID is represented in separate columns.

See Also

[get_dracor](#)

Examples

```
wiki_id <- "Q131412"  
get_character_plays(wiki_id)
```

get_dracor_meta *Retrieve information on available corpora*

Description

get_dracor_meta() returns metadata on available corpora as a dracor_meta object that inherits data frame (and can be used as such). Use summary() and plot() on this object to get an even more condensed summary.

Usage

```
get_dracor_meta()

## S3 method for class 'dracor_meta'
summary(object, ...)

## S3 method for class 'dracor_meta'
plot(x, ...)
```

Arguments

object	An object of class "dracor_meta".
...	Other arguments to be passed.
x	A dracor_meta object.

Value

dracor_meta object that inherits data frame (and can be used as such).

Functions

- `summary(dracor_meta)`: Meaningful summary for dracor_meta object.
- `plot(dracor_meta)`: Plots how many plays are available for each corpus.

See Also

[get_dracor](#)

Examples

```
corpora_meta <- get_dracor_meta()
corpora_meta
summary(corpora_meta)
plot(corpora_meta)
```

`get_net_cooccur_edges` *Retrieve co-occurrence edges list for a play as a data frame*

Description

`get_net_cooccur_edges()` requests edges list for a play network, given corpus and play names. Each row represents co-occurrences of two characters in a play — number of scenes where two characters appeared together. This edges list can be used to construct a network for a play.

Usage

```
get_net_cooccur_edges(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, ...)
```

```
get_net_relations_edges(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, ...)
```

Arguments

play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
...	Additional arguments passed to dracor_api .

Value

data frame with edges (each row = one edge of a network).

Functions

- [get_net_relations_edges\(\)](#): Retrieves kinship and other relationship data, following the encoding scheme proposed in (Wiedmer et al. 2020).

References

Wiedmer N, Pagel J, Reiter N (2020). "Romeo, Freund des Mercutio: Semi-Automatische Extraktion von Beziehungen zwischen dramatischen Figuren." In *Konferenz Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.4621778.

See Also

[get_net_cooccur_igraph](#) [get_net_cooccur_gexf](#) [get_net_cooccur_graphml](#) [get_net_cooccur_metrics](#)
[get_net_relations_igraph](#)

Examples

```
get_net_cooccur_edges(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
```

`get_net_cooccur_gexf` Retrieve co-occurrence network for a play in 'GEXF'

Description

`get_net_cooccur_gexf()` requests a play co-occurrence network in 'GEXF' (Graph Exchange XML Format), given play and corpus names. 'GEXF' is a format used in 'Gephi' — an open source software for network analysis and visualization.

Usage

```
get_net_cooccur_gexf(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, parse = TRUE, ...)
```

```
get_net_relations_gexf(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, ...)
```

Arguments

play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by <code>get_dracor</code>). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by <code>get_dracor_meta</code>).
parse	Logical, if TRUE the result is parsed by <code>xml2::read_xml()</code> , otherwise character value is returned. Default value is TRUE.
...	Additional arguments passed to <code>dracor_api</code> .

Value

'GEXF' data.

Functions

- `get_net_relations_gexf()`: Retrieves kinship and other relationship data, following the encoding scheme proposed in (Wiedmer et al. 2020).

References

Wiedmer N, Pagel J, Reiter N (2020). "Romeo, Freund des Mercutio: Semi-Automatische Extraktion von Beziehungen zwischen dramatischen Figuren." In *Konferenz Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.4621778.

See Also

[get_net_cooccur_igraph](#) [get_net_cooccur_metrics](#) [get_net_cooccur_graphml](#) [get_net_cooccur_edges](#)
[get_net_relations_igraph](#)

Examples

```
get_net_cooccur_gexf(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
# If you want 'GEXF' without parsing by xml2::read_xml():
get_net_cooccur_gexf(
  play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  corpus = "ger",
  parse = FALSE
)
```

 get_net_cooccur_graphml

Retrieve co-occurrence network for a play in 'GraphML'

Description

get_net_cooccur_graphml() requests a play co-occurrence network in 'GraphML', given play and corpus names. 'GraphML' is a common format for graphs based on XML.

Usage

```
get_net_cooccur_graphml(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, parse = TRUE, ...)
```

```
get_net_relations_graphml(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, ...)
```

Arguments

play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
parse	Logical, if TRUE the result is parsed by <code>xml2::read_xml()</code> , otherwise character value is returned. Default value is TRUE.
...	Additional arguments passed to dracor_api .

Value

'GraphML' data.

Functions

- `get_net_relations_graphml()`: Retrieves kinship and other relationship data, following the encoding scheme proposed in (Wiedmer et al. 2020).

References

Wiedmer N, Pagel J, Reiter N (2020). "Romeo, Freund des Mercutio: Semi-Automatische Extraktion von Beziehungen zwischen dramatischen Figuren." In *Konferenz Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.4621778.

See Also

[get_net_cooccur_igraph](#) [get_net_cooccur_gexf](#) [get_net_cooccur_metrics](#) [get_net_cooccur_edges](#)
[get_net_relations_igraph](#)

Examples

```
get_net_cooccur_graphml(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
# If you want 'GEXF' without parsing by xml2::read_xml():
get_net_cooccur_graphml(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger", parse = FALSE)
```

```
get_net_cooccur_igraph
```

Retrieve an igraph co-occurrence network for a play

Description

get_net_cooccur_igraph() returns a play network, given play and corpus names. Play network is constructed based on characters' co-occurrence matrix. Each node (vertex) is a character (circle) or a group of characters (square), edges width is proportional to the number of common play segments where two characters occur together.

Usage

```
get_net_cooccur_igraph(play = NULL, corpus = NULL)

## S3 method for class 'cooccur_igraph'
plot(
  x,
  layout = igraph::layout_with_kk,
  vertex.label = label_cooccur_igraph(x),
  gender_colors = c(MALE = "#0073C2", FEMALE = "#EFC000", UNKNOWN = "#99979D"),
  vertex_size_metric = c("numOfWords", "numOfScenes", "numOfSpeechActs", "degree",
    "weightedDegree", "closeness", "betweenness", "eigenvector"),
  vertex_size_scale = c(5, 20),
  edge_size_scale = c(0.5, 4),
  vertex_label_adjust = TRUE,
  vertex.label.color = "#03070f",
  vertex.label.family = "sans",
  vertex.label.font = 2L,
  vertex.frame.color = "white",
  ...
)

## S3 method for class 'cooccur_igraph'
summary(object, ...)
```

Arguments

play Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by [get_dracor](#)). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.

corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
x	A cooccur_igraph object to plot.
layout	Function, an algorithm used for the graph layout. See igraph.plotting .
vertex.label	Character vector of character names. By default, function label_cooccur_igraph is used to avoid overplotting on large graphs.
gender_colors	Named vector with 3 values with colors for MALE, FEMALE and UNKNOWN respectively. Set NULL to use the default igraph colors. If you set parameter <code>vertex.color</code> (see igraph.plotting), <code>gender_colors</code> will be ignored.
vertex_size_metric	Character value, one of "numOfWords", "numOfScenes", "numOfSpeechActs", "degree", "weightedDegree", "closeness", "betweenness", "eigenvector" that will be used as a metric for vertex size. Alternatively, you can specify vertex size by yourself using parameter <code>vertex.size</code> (see igraph.plotting), in this case parameter <code>vertex_size_metric</code> is ignored.
vertex_size_scale	Numeric vector with two values. The first number is for mean size of node(vertex), the second one is for node size variance. If you specify vertex size by yourself using parameter <code>vertex.size</code> (see igraph.plotting), <code>vertex_size_scale</code> is ignored.
edge_size_scale	Numeric vector with two values. The first number defines average size of edges, the second number defines edges size variance. If you specify edges size by yourself using parameter <code>edge.width</code> (see igraph.plotting), <code>edge_size_scale</code> is ignored.
vertex_label_adjust	Logical. If TRUE, labels positions are moved to the top of the respective nodes. If FALSE, labels are placed in the nodes centers. TRUE by default. If you set parameter <code>vertex.label.dist</code> (see igraph.plotting) by yourself, <code>vertex_label_adjust</code> is ignored.
vertex.label.color	See igraph.plotting .
vertex.label.family	See igraph.plotting .
vertex.label.font	See igraph.plotting .
vertex.frame.color	See igraph.plotting .
...	Other arguments to be passed to plot.igraph
object	An object of class <code>cooccur_igraph</code> .

Value

`cooccur_igraph` — an object that inherits `igraph` and can be treated as such.

Functions

- `plot(cooccur_igraph)`: Plot `cooccur_igraph` using `plot.igraph` with slightly modified defaults.
- `summary(cooccur_igraph)`: Meaningful summary for "`cooccur_igraph`" object: network properties, gender distribution

See Also

[get_net_relations_igraph](#) [label_cooccur_igraph](#)

Examples

```
emilia_igraph <- get_net_cooccur_igraph(
  play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  corpus = "ger"
)
igraph::diameter(emilia_igraph)
plot(emilia_igraph)
summary(emilia_igraph)
```

```
get_net_cooccur_metrics
```

Retrieve co-occurrence network metrics for a play

Description

`get_net_cooccur_metrics()` requests network metrics for a specific play, given play and corpus names. Play network is constructed based on characters' co-occurrence matrix.

Usage

```
get_net_cooccur_metrics(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, ...)
```

Arguments

<code>play</code>	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
<code>corpus</code>	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
<code>...</code>	Additional arguments passed to dracor_api .

Value

List with network metrics for a specific play.

See Also

[get_net_cooccur_igraph](#) [get_net_cooccur_gexf](#) [get_net_cooccur_graphml](#) [get_net_cooccur_edges](#)
[get_net_relations_igraph](#)

Examples

```
get_net_cooccur_metrics(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
```

```
get_net_relations_igraph
```

Retrieve an igraph relations network for a play

Description

`get_net_relations_igraph()` a play network, given play and corpus names . The network represent kinship and other relationships data, following the encoding scheme proposed in (Wiedmer et al. 2020).

Usage

```
get_net_relations_igraph(play = play, corpus = corpus)
```

```
## S3 method for class 'relations_igraph'  
summary(object, ...)
```

```
## S3 method for class 'relations_igraph'  
plot(  
  x,  
  layout = igraph::layout_nicely,  
  gender_colors = c(MALE = "#0073C2", FEMALE = "#EFC000", UNKNOWN = "#99979D"),  
  show_others = c("vertex", "vertex_label", "none"),  
  vertex_size = c(13, 4),  
  vertex_label_size = c(0.8, 0.5),  
  vertex_label_adjust = TRUE,  
  vertex.label.color = "#03070f",  
  vertex.label.family = "sans",  
  vertex.label.font = 2L,  
  vertex.frame.color = "white",  
  edge.arrow.size = 0.25,  
  edge.arrow.width = 1.5,  
  edge.curved = 0.15,  
  edge.label.family = "sans",  
  edge.label.font = 4L,  
  edge.label.cex = 0.75,  
  ...  
)
```

Arguments

play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
object	An object of class relations_igraph.
...	Other arguments to be passed to plot.igraph
x	A relations_igraph object to plot.
layout	Function, an algorithm used for graph layout. See layout_ .
gender_colors	Named vector with 3 values with colors for MALE, FEMALE and UNKNOWN respectively. Set NULL to use default igraph colors. If you set parameter vertex.color (see igraph.plotting), gender_colors will be ignored.
show_others	Character value. What to do with vertices without relations? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "vertex": plot only vertices without labels. • "vertex_label": plot both vertices and labels. • "none": do not plot vertices without relations. <p>The default is "vertex".</p>
vertex_size	Numeric vector with two values. The first number is for nodes with relations, the second number is for all other nodes.
vertex_label_size	Numeric vector with two values. The first number defines label sizes for nodes with relations, the second number for nodes without relations.
vertex_label_adjust	Logical value. If TRUE, labels positions are moved to the top of the respective nodes. If FALSE, labels are placed in the nodes centers. TRUE by default. If you set parameter vertex.label.dist(see igraph.plotting) by yourself, vertex_label_adjust is ignored.
vertex.label.color	See igraph.plotting .
vertex.label.family	See igraph.plotting .
vertex.label.font	See igraph.plotting .
vertex.frame.color	See igraph.plotting .
edge.arrow.size	See igraph.plotting .
edge.arrow.width	See igraph.plotting .
edge.curved	See igraph.plotting .
edge.label.family	See igraph.plotting .

edge.label.font
See [igraph.plotting](#).
edge.label.cex See [igraph.plotting](#).

Value

relations_igraph — an object that inherits igraph and can be treated as such.

Functions

- `summary(relations_igraph)`: Meaningful summary for "relations_igraph" object: relationships and their type.
- `plot(relations_igraph)`: Plot relations_igraph using `plot.igraph` with slightly modified defaults.

References

Wiedmer N, Pagel J, Reiter N (2020). "Romeo, Freund des Mercutio: Semi-Automatische Extraktion von Beziehungen zwischen dramatischen Figuren." In *Konferenz Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.4621778.

See Also

[get_net_cooccur_igraph](#)

Examples

```
nedorosl_relations <- get_net_relations_igraph(  
  play = "fonvizin-nedorosl",  
  corpus = "rus"  
)  
plot(nedorosl_relations)  
summary(nedorosl_relations)
```

get_play_cast *Retrieve data for characters in a play*

Description

`get_play_cast()` requests miscellaneous information for characters in a play, given play and corpus names: name, number and size of their lines, gender, some network metrics etc.

Usage

```
get_play_cast(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, ...)
```

Arguments

play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
...	Additional arguments passed to dracor_api .

Value

Data frame, every row represents one character in the play.

See Also

[get_play_metadata](#)

Examples

```
get_play_cast(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
```

get_play_metadata *Retrieve metadata for a play*

Description

get_play_metadata() requests metadata for a specific play, given play and corpus names.

Usage

```
get_play_metadata(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, full_metadata = TRUE, ...)
```

Arguments

play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
full_metadata	Logical: if TRUE (default value), then additional metadata are retrieved.
...	Additional arguments passed to dracor_api .

Value

List with the play metadata.

See Also

[get_net_cooccur_edges](#) [get_play_rdf](#) [get_play_cast](#)

Examples

```
get_play_metadata(
  play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  corpus = "ger",
  full_metadata = FALSE
)
```

get_play_rdf

Retrieve an RDF for a play

Description

`get_play_rdf()` requests an RDF (Resource Description Framework) data for a play, given play and corpus names. RDF for plays can be useful for extraction data for a play from https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page.

Usage

```
get_play_rdf(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, parse = TRUE, ...)
```

Arguments

play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
parse	Logical, if TRUE the result is parsed by <code>xml2::read_xml()</code> , otherwise character value is returned. Default value is TRUE.
...	Additional arguments passed to dracor_api .

Value

RDF data parsed by `xml2::read_xml()`.

See Also

[get_play_metadata](#) [get_play_cast](#)

Examples

```
get_play_rdf(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
# If you want RDF without parsing by xml2::read_xml():
get_play_rdf(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger", parse = FALSE)
```

get_text_chr_spoken *Retrieve lines and stage directions for a play*

Description

get_text_chr_spoken() request lines and stage directions for a play, given play and corpus names.

Usage

```
get_text_chr_spoken(
  play = NULL,
  corpus = NULL,
  gender = NULL,
  split_text = TRUE,
  ...
)
```

```
get_text_chr_spoken_bych(
  play = NULL,
  corpus = NULL,
  split_text = TRUE,
  as_data_frame = FALSE,
  ...
)
```

```
get_text_chr_stage(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, split_text = TRUE, ...)
```

```
get_text_chr_stage_with_sp(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, split_text = TRUE, ...)
```

Arguments

play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
gender	Character, optional parameter to extract lines for characters of specified gender: "MALE", "FEMALE", "UNKNOWN".
split_text	If TRUE returns text as a character vector of lines. Otherwise, returns text as one character value. TRUE by default.
...	Additional arguments passed to dracor_api .
as_data_frame	If TRUE returns data frame with a row for every character and text in a column "text". Otherwise, a named list with character values is returned. FALSE by default.

Value

For `get_text_chr_spoken()`, `get_text_chr_stage()` and `get_text_chr_stage_with_sp()`: a character vector (if `split_text = TRUE`, the default value) or a single character value (if `split_text = FALSE`). For `get_text_chr_spoken_bych()`:

`split_text = TRUE` **and** `as_data_frame = FALSE` (**default**) a named list with character vectors for every character

`split_text = FALSE` **and** `as_data_frame = FALSE` a named character vector (one value = one character)

`split_text = TRUE` **and** `as_data_frame = TRUE` a data frame: every row represent a character, text of a play is stored in a "text" column, the "text" column is a list column with a character vector of lines

`split_text = FALSE` **and** `as_data_frame = TRUE` a data frame: every row represent a character, text of a play is stored in a "text" column, the "text" column is a simple character column

Functions

- `get_text_chr_spoken_bych()`: Retrieves lines grouped by characters in a play, given play and corpus names.
- `get_text_chr_stage()`: Retrieves all stage directions of a play, given play and corpus names.
- `get_text_chr_stage_with_sp()`: Retrieves all stage directions of a play including speakers (if applicable), given play and corpus names.

See Also

[get_text_tei](#) [get_text_df](#)

Examples

```
get_text_chr_spoken(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
get_text_chr_spoken(
  play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  corpus = "ger",
  gender = "FEMALE"
)
get_text_chr_spoken(
  play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  corpus = "ger",
  gender = "FEMALE",
  split_text = FALSE
)
get_text_chr_spoken_bych(
  play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  corpus = "ger"
)
get_text_chr_stage(
  play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  corpus = "ger"
```

```

)
get_text_chr_stage_with_sp(
  play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  corpus = "ger"
)

```

get_text_tei	Retrieve a text for a play in 'TEI'
--------------	-------------------------------------

Description

get_text_tei() requests a text for a play in 'TEI' format, given play and corpus names. 'TEI' is an XML vocabulary, which makes it easy to extract structural information (Fischer et al. 2019).

Usage

```
get_text_tei(play = NULL, corpus = NULL, ...)
```

Arguments

play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).
...	Additional arguments passed to dracor_api .

Value

TEI data parsed by [xml2::read_xml\(\)](#).

References

Fischer F, Börner I, Göbel M, Hecht A, Kittel C, Milling C, Trilcke P (2019). "Programmable corpora: Introducing DraCor, an infrastructure for the research on European drama." In *Digital Humanities 2019: "Complexities" (DH2019)*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.4284002.

See Also

[get_text_df](#) [get_text_chr_spoken](#) [tei_to_df](#)

Examples

```

get_text_tei(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
# If you want a text in TEI without parsing by xml2::read_xml():
get_text_tei(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger", parse = FALSE)

```

label_cooccur_igraph *Extract labels for plotting 'cooccur_igraph' object*

Description

label_cooccur_igraph() returns labels for plotting cooccur_igraph object. label_cooccur_igraph gives control of overplotting for labels (i.e. character names) by deleting extra labels if there are too many of them. Thus, it highlights the most significant characters of the selected play. This function can be used to set vertex.label parameter for [plot.cooccur_igraph](#).

Usage

```
label_cooccur_igraph(  
  graph,  
  max_graph_size = 30L,  
  top_nodes = 3L,  
  label_size_metric = c("betweenness", "numOfWords", "numOfScenes", "numOfSpeechActs",  
    "degree", "weightedDegree", "closeness", "eigenvector")  
)
```

Arguments

graph	cooccur_igraph object to plot.
max_graph_size	Integer, maximum network size for plotting all labels. If you don't want to delete any labels, set Inf.
top_nodes	Integer, number of labels to be plotted. Characters with the highest number of words will be selected.
label_size_metric	Character, a metric that is used to rank characters in a play.

Details

label_cooccur_igraph takes labels from a vertices data frame column "name", checks that network size is more than max_graph_size, if it is true, returns names for top top_nodes and NA for the rest.

Value

Character vector of character names.

See Also

[get_net_cooccur_igraph](#)

Examples

```
emilia_igraph <- get_net_cooccur_igraph(
  play = "lessing-emilia-galotti",
  corpus = "ger"
)
label_cooccur_igraph(emilia_igraph, max_graph_size = 10, top_nodes = 4)
```

summary.dracor

Retrieve metadata for all plays in selected corpora

Description

get_dracor() request data on all plays in selected (or all) corpora. get_dracor() returns dracor object that inherits data frame (and can be used as such) but specified [summary](#) method.

Usage

```
## S3 method for class 'dracor'
summary(object, ...)

get_dracor(corpus = "all", full_metadata = TRUE)
```

Arguments

object	An object of class dracor.
...	Other arguments to be passed to summary.default .
corpus	Character vector with names of the corpora (you can find all corpora names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta) or "all" (default value). if "all", then all available corpora are downloaded.
full_metadata	Logical: if TRUE (default value), then additional metadata are retrieved.

Details

You need to provide a vector with valid names of the corpora, e.g. "rus", "ger" or "shake". Use function [get_dracor_meta](#) to extract names for all available corpora.

Value

dracor object that inherits data frame (and can be used as such).

Functions

- summary(dracor): Meaningful summary for dracor_meta object.

See Also[get_dracor_meta](#)**Examples**

```
tat <- get_dracor("tat")
summary(tat)
get_dracor(c("ita", "span", "greek"))
get_dracor()
```

tei_to_df	<i>Retrieve a text for a play as a data frame</i>
-----------	---

Description

The function `get_text_df()` returns you a data frame with text of the selected play. `tei_to_df()` allows to convert an existing 'TEI' object to a data frame.

Usage

```
tei_to_df(tei)

get_text_df(play, corpus)
```

Arguments

tei	A TEI object stored as an object of class <code>xml_document</code> . You can use this function if you have already downloaded TEI using get_text_tei .
play	Character, name of a play (you can find all play names in "playName" column within an object returned by get_dracor). Character vector (longer than 1) is not supported.
corpus	Character, name of the corpus (you can find all corpus names in name column within an object returned by get_dracor_meta).

Value

Text of a play as a data frame in **tidy text** format. Each row represent one token. The text tokenised by lines, notes and stage directions (`<p>`, `<l>`, `<stage>` or `<note>`). Column `text` contains text of the line, other columns contain metadata for the line.

Functions

- `get_text_df()`: Retrieves all stage directions of a play, given play and corpus names.

See Also[get_play_metadata](#)**Examples**

```
get_text_df(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
emilia_tei <- get_text_tei(play = "lessing-emilia-galotti", corpus = "ger")
tei_to_df(emilia_tei)
```

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D7.2 DraCor API Libraries for R and Python

Appendix 3: “pydracor” Readme

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pydracor 1.0.0

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```
pip install pydracor
```


Released: Feb 23, 2023

Python package which provides access to the DraCor API.

Navigation

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GitHub statistics:

★ **Stars: 3**🔗 **Forks: 0**! **Open issues: 10**🔗 **Open PRs: 0**

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Project description

pydracor

pydracor is a Python package which provides access to the [DraCor API](#).

Acknowledgment:

The development of this package was supported by Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA). CLS INFRA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984.

Classes

- *DraCor*

Base class used to represent Drama Corpus entity. DraCor consists of Corpora.

- *Corpus*

A class used to represent a Corpus of DraCor. Corpus (als/bash/cal/fre/ger/gersh/greek/hun/ita/rom/rus/shake/span/swe/tat) consists of plays.

using [our public dataset on Google BigQuery](#) [↗](#)

Meta

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📖 drama corpus,
drama, corpus,
pydracor, dracor, api,
wrapper

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Classifiers

Development Status

- [4 - Beta](#)

Intended Audience

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Programming Language

- [Python](#)
- [Python :: 3](#)
- [Python :: 3.6](#)
- [Python :: 3.7](#)
- [Python :: 3.8](#)

- [Play](#)

A class used to represent a Play of a Corpus. Play consists of Characters.

- [Character](#)

A class used to represent a Character of a Play.

Code examples

Import all classes

```
>>> from pydracor import *
```

Dracor

- Initialize a *DraCor* instance

```
>>> dracor = DraCor()
```

- Summary in a dictionary

```
>>> dracor.summary()
```

- Summary in a string

```
>>> str(dracor)
```

- DraCor info in a dictionary

```
>>> dracor.dracor_info()
```

- List available corpora in DraCor

```
>>> dracor.corpora()
>>> dracor.corpora(include='metrics')
```

- List available corpora names in DraCor

- Python :: 3.9

Topic

- Education
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- Software Development :: Libraries
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```
>>> dracor.corpora_names()
```

- List available corpora titles in DraCor

```
>>> dracor.corpora_titles()
```

- Map X to Y

```
>>> dracor.corpus_name_to_repository()
>>> dracor.corpus_name_to_title()
>>> dracor.corpus_name_to_uri()
>>> dracor.play_title_to_corpus_name()
>>> dracor.play_title_to_play_id()
>>> dracor.play_name_to_corpus_name()
>>> dracor.play_name_to_play_id()
>>> dracor.play_id_to_play_title()
>>> dracor.play_id_to_play_name()
```

- Submit SPARQL queries with query parameter

```
>>> dracor.sparql("PREFIX urn: <http://fliqz.com/> SELEC
```

Corpus

- Initialize a *Corpus* instance

```
>>> corpus = Corpus('rus')
>>> corpus = Corpus('cal')
...

```

- Summary in a dictionary

```
>>> corpus.summary()
```

- Summary in a string

```
>>> str(corpus)
```

- Authors' summary for a corpus

```
>>> corpus.authors_summary()
>>> corpus.authors_summary(num_of_authors=5)
```

- String representation of authors_summary method

```
>>> corpus.authors_summary_str()
>>> corpus.authors_summary_str(num_of_authors=5)
```

- Corpus info in a dictionary

```
>>> corpus.corpus_info()
```

- Get all corpus' play Xs

```
>>> corpus.play_ids()
>>> corpus.play_names()
>>> corpus.play_titles()
```

- Map play id to the X year

```
>>> corpus.written_years()
>>> corpus.premiere_years()
>>> corpus.premiere_years()
```

- List of metadata for all plays in a corpus

```
>>> corpus.metadata()
```

- Filter Plays of a Corpus

Filters are equivalent to the django filters

Possible relations: *eq / ne / gt / ge / lt / le / contains / icontains / exact / iexact / in*

Possible fields: all the attributes that the *Corpus* instance contains

```
>>> corpus.filter(written_year__eq=1913, network_size__l
>>> corpus.filter(print_year__lt=1850, source__icontains
>>> corpus.filter(
    id__in=frozenset(f"rus000{num:03d}" for num in range
    subtitle__icontains='комедия',
```

```
        author__name__contains='Крылов'  
    )  
>>> corpus.filter(name__contains='mysl')  
>>> corpus.filter(title__exact='Мысль')  
>>> corpus.filter(  
    year_normalized__in=frozenset(['1935', '1936'])  
    source_url__contains='lib'  
)  
>>> corpus.filter(wikidata_id__iexact='Q1989636')  
>>> corpus.filter(networkdata_csv_url__icontains='/andre')  
>>> corpus.filter(authors__name__icontains='Бабель')
```

Play

- Initialize a *Play* instance

If *play_id* is not None, *play_name* and *play_title* are not considered

If *play_id* is None AND *play_name* is not None, *play_title* is not considered

If *play_id* is None AND *play_name* is None, *play_title* should not be None, otherwise *ValueError* is raised

If *play_id* is None, automatic corpus detection is applied

```
>>> play = Play('rus000160')  
>>> play = Play(play_id='rus000160')  
>>> play = Play(play_name='ostrovsky-dohodnoe-mesto')  
>>> play = Play(play_title='Доходное место')
```

- Summary in a dictionary

```
>>> play.summary()
```

- Summary in a string

```
>>> str(play)
```

- Play info in a dictionary

```
>>> play.play_info()
```

- Get network metrics for a single play

```
>>> play.metrics()
```

- Get a list of characters of a play

```
>>> play.get_cast()
```

- Get X of a play

```
>>> play.num_of_male_characters
>>> play.num_of_female_characters
>>> play.num_of_unknown_characters
>>> play.tei
>>> play.rdf
>>> play.csv
>>> play.gexf
```

- Get spoken text of a play (excluding stage directions)

```
>>> play.spoken_text()
>>> play.spoken_text(gender='MALE')
>>> play.spoken_text(gender='FEMALE')
>>> play.spoken_text(gender='UNKNOWN')
```

- Get spoken text for each character of a play

```
>>> play.spoken_text_by_character()
```

- Get all stage directions of a play

```
>>> play.stage_directions()
```

- Get all stage directions of a play including speakers

```
>>> play.stage_directions_with_speakers()
```

Character

- Initialize a *Character* instance

```
>>> character = Character('yakov', 'rus000138')
>>> character = Character('kraft', 'rus000137')
...

```

- Summary in a dictionary

```
>>> character.summary()

```

- Summary in a string

```
>>> str(character)

```

Installation

```
$ pip install pydracor

```

Todos

- write more methods
- write more tests

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Error logging

StatusPage
Status page